

Association between job satisfaction, perceived burnout, stress, and health status among pharmacists in northeastern Bulgaria

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Abstract

Expanding pharmacist roles in modern healthcare systems, together with the associated workload, creates a need to examine professional satisfaction and perceptions of overload. Professional well-being among pharmacists is shaped by a complex interaction of organizational, professional, and individual factors, providing a basis for investigating the relationships among job satisfaction, stress, perceived burnout, and health status. A direct anonymous survey was conducted using a semi-structured questionnaire among 127 Master of Pharmacy professionals in northeastern Bulgaria. Sociodemographic characteristics did not show a statistically significant effect.

Positive correlations were found between satisfaction and remuneration ($\rho = 0.380$), professional development ($\rho = 0.457$), relationships with colleagues ($\rho = 0.393$), and willingness to choose the profession again ($\rho = 0.410$). Stress was associated with additional workload ($\rho = 0.352$). A negative relationship was observed between satisfaction and perceived burnout ($\rho = -0.210$), while a positive relationship was found between stress and perceived burnout ($\rho = 0.216$). Physical activity was positively associated with health status ($\rho = 0.266$). The results highlight the role of the organizational environment and psycho-emotional workload.

Keywords

Health status, job satisfaction, Master pharmacists, perceived burnout, stress

Introduction

Professional satisfaction is an important indicator of the quality of working life and of the sustainable functioning of the healthcare system (Van Laar et al. 2007; Tosheva et al. 2023; Hoxha et al. 2024). It reflects the extent to which a professional believes that their job matches their expectations in terms of professional independence, compensation, interpersonal connections, workplace atmosphere, development prospects, and recognition (Carvajal and Popovici 2018; Donley 2021; Cherecheş et al. 2024). Professional

satisfaction is especially important in the health professions because it is linked to the well-being of professionals, as well as the quality, safety, and effectiveness of the care provided (Mattsson and Gustafsson 2020; Alkhateeb et al. 2025). The pharmacy profession has moved from a mostly technical job involving the formulation and distribution of pharmaceuticals to a more complicated professional function focused on pharmaceutical care and clinical practice. In contemporary practice, pharmacists work as members of interdisciplinary teams and are involved in medication therapy management, prevention, and chronic disease

monitoring. This transformation is driven by developments in healthcare, technological advances, and the increased role of pharmacotherapy and pharmaceutical care and is accompanied by increased professional workload and stress, which raise the risk of burnout (Gavazova et al. 2025). The investigation of professional satisfaction and the variables that influence it is becoming increasingly crucial as the function of pharmacists in the healthcare system grows. The quality of pharmaceutical care and patient safety are linked to the professional well-being of pharmacists. According to FIP, a safe and supportive work environment is important for quality care, and professional burnout may adversely affect patients (IPF 2025).

The profession of the Master of Pharmacy is characterized by a high degree of public and health accountability in this context, and it has also required continual adaptation to the changing demands of patients and healthcare systems in recent years (Isenor et al. 2023; Muscat et al. 2024; Clemens et al. 2025). The work environment is characterized by significant labor intensity, organizational pressure, and the need for ongoing adaptation to regulatory, organizational, and technological requirements (Kato et al. 2024; Ogundipe et al. 2025). An excessive workload, changes in the amount and content of work, and a decline in the quality of one's professional life may eventually become a continuous source of stress and increase the risk of burnout (Dee et al. 2023; Kato et al. 2024). According to the World Health Organization, burnout is an occupational condition caused by chronic and unmanaged workplace stress. It manifests in three key dimensions: exhaustion, psychological detachment from or cynicism about work, and decreased professional effectiveness (WHO 2019).

Stress, burnout, and job satisfaction are frequently considered related facets of professional well-being in the scientific literature (Tosheva and Tarpomanova 2023). In contrast, chronic workload and organizational pressure raise the likelihood of emotional exhaustion, demotivation, and withdrawal from the professional role (Katsogiannis et al. 2024; Barakat and Sallam 2025; Gavazova et al. 2025; Gustafsson et al. 2025; Neykova-Sidorenko et al. 2025), whereas lower job satisfaction is frequently linked to higher levels of stress. According to a study by Dee et al. (2023), burnout is a prevalent issue among pharmacists, with the main risk factors being high workload, long working hours, poor work-life balance, and aspects of the work environment. The significance of the workplace and working conditions for pharmacists' professional well-being is highlighted by Stavrou et al. (2022), who discovered a link between higher levels of occupational stress and reduced job satisfaction. In this context, the specific character of the organizational environment in pharmacy practice becomes particularly important, as it is shaped not only by working conditions but also by legal and regulatory requirements.

In Bulgaria, the focus is on compliance with the legislative framework, which calls for a shift in approach and a deeper analysis of the interplay between stress, organizational and motivational factors, and job satisfaction. Investigating the individual and organizational

factors influencing professional satisfaction will provide a clear perspective on the need to introduce changes in the work environment and to develop individual approaches for motivating practicing community pharmacists.

The aim of the study is to identify the organizational, professional, and sociodemographic factors that affect professional satisfaction, stress, and burnout among Master of Pharmacy professionals in northeastern Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Study design

A pilot cross-sectional sociological study was conducted using a direct anonymous paper-based survey aimed at a one-time assessment of professional satisfaction, stress, and perceived burnout among Master of Pharmacy professionals working in community pharmacies in northeastern Bulgaria.

Study setting

The pilot study was conducted between March 2024 and October 2024 among Master of Pharmacy professionals in the city of Varna, the largest city in the region.

Participants

A total of 127 Master of Pharmacy professionals who met the predefined inclusion criteria and provided informed consent to participate were included in the study. The sample size is consistent with the study's pilot character (Whitehead et al. 2016). The data gathered, although not fully representative of the target population, allow for analysis of the primary trends and relationships between the variables studied.

Inclusion criteria: Master of Pharmacy professionals who were members of the Varna Regional Pharmaceutical Chamber, completed an informed consent form, and were working in community pharmacies.

Exclusion criteria: pharmacy students, assistant pharmacists, Master of Pharmacy professionals who were not members of the Varna Regional Pharmaceutical Chamber, those who had not completed an informed consent form, Master of Pharmacy professionals who were not employed in community pharmacies, and those with incomplete or improperly completed questionnaires.

Instrument

Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire developed by the authors for the purposes of this pilot study. The questionnaire was designed based on a literature review focusing on job satisfaction, work-related stress, organizational environment, opportunities for professional development, and perceived burnout within the pharmacy profession. The instrument consisted entirely

of author-developed questions tailored to the Bulgarian context; no validated psychometric scales were used, and no items were directly adopted from existing instruments.

To ensure the clarity and comprehensibility of the questionnaire items, a pilot study was conducted among a small group of pharmacists ($n = 25$), with no significant difficulties or ambiguities identified.

The pilot study aimed to explore initial response patterns and assess the feasibility of the instrument for future refinement and validation. The final questionnaire consisted of 15 items (12 closed-ended and three open-ended), organized into four thematic domains:

- Professional satisfaction;
- Characteristics of the organizational environment and opportunities for professional development;
- Stress levels and perceived burnout;
- Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants.

Data collection

Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous. Data were collected in a real work environment through the direct distribution of paper-based questionnaires. Each participant was informed in advance about the purpose of the study, as well as the storage and processing of the data. Respondents completed the questionnaire only after signing an informed consent form. The study was conducted under conditions of guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality, and no personal data enabling participant identification were collected. The information obtained was used solely for scientific purposes and processed in aggregated form. Only the research team had access to the primary data.

The methods used in the study were sociological and statistical.

Data analysis

Statistical data processing was performed using jamovi 2.6, software based on R for statistical analysis and for testing relationships and associations.

The following statistical methods were used for data analysis:

- The relationship between variables was analyzed using Spearman's correlation (ρ) for ordinal variables and ranked data;
- Pearson's correlation (r) was used for variables treated as approximately interval-level;
- Linear regression was applied for dependent variables treated as quantitative variables (scale scores);
- Binary logistic regression was used for dichotomous dependent variables (yes/no responses).

Ethical considerations: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Medical University—Varna, Protocol No. 135/28.09.2023.

Study limitations

A limitation of the study is that perceived burnout was assessed through self-reported evaluation rather than a validated standardized instrument, limiting comparability with other studies conducted among pharmacists. Additionally, the use of subjective self-assessment for some variables may increase variability in responses and introduce potential bias.

Results

The study included 127 Master of Pharmacy practitioners who satisfied the eligibility requirements. Table 1 shows the sociodemographic profile of the sample.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics.

Variable	Category	N	%
Sex	Female	91	75,8
	Male	29	24,2
Age	21–30 years	36	29,8
	31–40 years	28	23,1
	41–50 years	30	24,8
	51–60 years	20	16,5
	Over 61 years	7	5,8
Years of professional experience	Up to 1 year	13	10,2
	1–10 years	55	43,3
	11–20 years	21	16,5
	Over 20 years	35	27,6

Statistical processing and analysis were carried out to study the relationship between job satisfaction and associated variables using the gathered data. The percentage distribution of men and women is close to that reported in published sector data, according to which the majority of employees are female (Krumov and Grigorov 2019). The age group over 61 years had the smallest share of respondents (5.8%). The minimum age of the participants was 21 years, and the maximum was 70 years. The mean age of the sample was 40.6 years, with a median age of 39 years. Master of Pharmacy professionals with 1 to 10 years of professional experience predominated (43.3%).

Job satisfaction and its relationship with sociodemographic characteristics—sex, age, and professional experience—are presented in Table 2.

The analyses did not show a statistically significant association between job satisfaction and sex, age, or professional experience. Stress and sex or age showed no statistically significant correlation, nor did perceived burnout and sex or age.

These results indicate that, within the group studied, demographic characteristics are not among the determining factors of professional satisfaction. Rather, in accordance with the literature, more significance seems to be connected with factors pertaining to the organizational environment and professional development—remuneration, opportunities for advancement, peer relationships, and a comfortable working environment—as well as psychosocial and

Table 2. Association of demographic characteristics with job satisfaction, stress, and perceived burnout.

Dependent variable	Predictor	Coefficient (B/OR)	p-value	Method
Job satisfaction	Sex (male vs. female)	$B = -0.161$	0.457	Linear regression
	Age	$B = 0.022$	0.121	
	Professional experience	Professional experience 1–10 years (vs. ≤ 1 year)	$B = 0.513$	0.098
		Professional experience 11–20 years (vs. ≤ 1 year)	$B = -0.148$	0.712
		Professional experience > 20 years (vs. ≤ 1 year)	$B = -0.153$	0.757
Stress	Sex	$B = -0.088$	0.812	Linear regression
	Age	$B = -0.006$	0.685	Linear regression
Perceived burnout	Sex	OR = 1.207	0.767	Binary logistic regression
	Age	OR = 0.971	0.182	Binary logistic regression

health-related markers, including perceived stress, evidence of professional burnout, and health status (Table 3). This supports the interpretation of professional satisfaction as a multifactorial construct shaped primarily by working conditions and psycho-emotional workload.

The correlation analysis showed a statistically significant moderate positive association between job satisfaction and income ($\rho = 0.380, p < 0.001$), opportunities for professional development ($\rho = 0.457, p < 0.001$), willingness to choose the profession again ($\rho = 0.410, p < 0.001$), and collegial relationships ($\rho = 0.393, p < 0.001$). Job satisfaction was also statistically significantly related to comfort in the workplace ($\rho = -0.314, p = 0.001$). The coding of the variable, in which lower values signify comfort, explains the neg-

Table 3. Correlations between professional satisfaction and organizational, professional, psychosocial, and health-related factors.

Main variable	Related variable	Coefficient	p-value	Method
Job satisfaction	Remuneration	$\rho = 0.380$	< 0.001	Spearman
	Professional development	$\rho = 0.457$	< 0.001	Spearman
	Willingness to choose the profession again	$\rho = 0.410$	< 0.001	Spearman
	Comfort in the organization	$\rho = -0.314$	0.001	Spearman
	collegial relations	$\rho = 0.393$	< 0.001	Spearman
Stress level	Additional workload	$\rho = 0.352$	< 0.001	Spearman
	Willingness to choose the profession again	$\rho = -0.013$	0.887	Spearman
	Health status	$r = -0.176$	0.055	Spearman
Perceived burnout	Balance between rights and responsibilities	$\rho = -0.128$	0.161	Spearman
	Remuneration	$\rho = -0.155$	0.093	Spearman
Health status	Physical activity	$\rho = 0.266$	0.003	Spearman

ative direction of the correlation. Higher job satisfaction is therefore related to greater comfort in the organization.

Concerning stress level, a statistically significant moderate positive association was found with higher subjective perceived stress ($\rho = 0.352, p < 0.001$), suggesting that greater workload correlates with more subjectively perceived stress. Between willingness to choose the profession again and stress, no statistically significant link was observed ($\rho = -0.013, p = 0.887$). The relationship between stress and self-rated health status was negative but did not reach statistical significance ($r = -0.176, p = 0.055$).

Although weak negative trends existed, the perceived prevalence of professional burnout and neither the balance between rights and responsibilities ($\rho = -0.128, p = 0.161$) nor pay ($\rho = -0.155, p = 0.093$) showed statistically significant connections. Between self-rated health status and physical activity, a statistically significant weak positive correlation was observed ($\rho = 0.266, p = 0.003$), suggesting better self-rated health with higher levels of physical activity.

Following the analysis of the links between the major study variables and the relevant organizational, professional, psychological, and health-related factors, the associations among the primary variables themselves—job satisfaction, stress level, perceived presence of burnout in the profession, and health status—were also examined (Table 4).

Table 4. Associations between job satisfaction, stress, perceived burnout, and health status.

Variable 1	Variable 2	Coefficient	p-value	Method
Job satisfaction	Perceived burnout	$\rho = -0.210$	0.026	Spearman
Perceived burnout	Stress level	$\rho = 0.216$	0.017	Spearman
Stress level	Health status	$r = -0.176$	0.055	Pearson's

Among the factors investigated, weak relationships were found. Job satisfaction and perceived burnout in the profession were statistically significantly negatively related ($\rho = -0.210, p = 0.026$), indicating that respondents with higher job satisfaction were less likely to perceive burnout as a problem characteristic of the profession. A statistically significant positive correlation was also identified between the perceived presence of burnout in the profession and stress level ($\rho = 0.216, p = 0.017$), suggesting that respondents with higher levels of stress more frequently reported the existence of burnout in the professional environment. Furthermore, between stress level and health status, a weak negative but statistically non-significant correlation was observed ($r = -0.176, p = 0.055$). Therefore, it may be suggested that higher stress tends to be associated with a less favorable self-assessment of health.

These results should be interpreted with consideration that the burnout variable reflects not a personal experience of the syndrome but rather a perception of its presence in the profession. The observed correlational relationships indicate that the perceived presence of burnout in the profession is negatively associated with job satisfaction and positively associated with stress level.

Discussion

The lack of statistically significant links with sociodemographic factors in the present study implies that job satisfaction is more strongly affected by characteristics of the work environment and professional realization than by age, sex, and professional experience. Other studies have shown comparable results; age or sex were not particularly linked with job satisfaction, although emphasis was given to the role of factors connected to working conditions and career advancement (Gavazova et al. 2025; Gustafsson et al. 2025).

Results from the present study indicate that professional success among Master of Pharmacy professionals is mostly defined by organizational and professional factors. Strong correlations with pay, growth prospects, willingness to choose the profession again, collegial connections, and organizational comfort support the conclusion that features of the professional setting are more important than the individual qualities of the professionals themselves. Other authors have discovered similar links; they highlight remuneration, professional growth, collegial relationships, and organizational environment as significant contributors to job satisfaction among pharmacists (Mattsson and Gustafsson 2020; Meilianti et al. 2022; Radwan et al. 2022; Fadare et al. 2023; Alshahrani et al. 2025; Barakat and Sallam 2025). Moreover, supporting these results are data from prior studies indicating that 56% of active master's-level pharmacists dislike their workplace and would change it, while 71% would choose pharmacy once more as their career choice. Women more frequently choose work that matches their preference for a supportive and positive work environment; men prioritize compensation and career development possibilities (Ivanova 2023; Ivanova et al. 2024).

A statistically significant moderate positive correlation between stress level and additional workload strengthens the viewpoint that excessive work engagement, extended working hours, and impaired work-life balance act as major preconditions for higher psychological stress among pharmacists (Dee et al. 2023). Although weak negative tendencies were observed, no statistically significant associations were found with the balance between rights and responsibilities or with compensation regarding perceived burnout. This means that perceptions of professional burnout are shaped by a wider range of elements than by isolated evaluations of specific organizational qualities.

Although statistically non-significant, the negative correlation between stress and health status suggests a tendency for greater occupational stress to be linked to lower self-rated health and reduced quality of life (Katsogiannis et al. 2024). The observed positive connection between physical activity and self-rated health (Södergren et al. 2008) supports the view that physical activity and a better lifestyle may contribute favorably to pharmacists' general well-being. Common risk elements for musculoskeletal problems were sedentary behavior and little exercise (Tsvetkova et al. 2024).

The negative association between job satisfaction and reported perceived burnout in the field suggests that those with greater job satisfaction are less likely to see burnout as a defining feature of their professional practice. Concurrent-

ly, the positive association between perceived burnout and level of stress points to a stronger perception of professional burnout among pharmacists in higher-stress situations. These findings support research showing that burnout is linked to poor quality of life, decreased job satisfaction, and greater mental stress (Katsogiannis et al. 2024).

Although these results follow existing research, certain methodological issues should be acknowledged when analyzing the data. Particularly for perceived burnout, which reflects subjective judgment rather than clinically confirmed assessment, the reliance on self-reported measures may have influenced the accuracy of the observed correlations.

Therefore, the reported correlations between job satisfaction, stress, and perceived burnout should be approached carefully. Future studies should incorporate more objective indicators and certified measuring instruments to improve dependability and enable more thorough comparisons with already published studies among pharmacists.

Conclusion

Professional satisfaction among Master of Pharmacy professionals is a multifaceted phenomenon that depends more on organizational and professional elements than on sociodemographic traits. The most significant factors are compensation, career advancement opportunities, collegial relationships, and comfort inside the organization.

The identified connections highlight the relationship of professional satisfaction to both stress level and perceived existence of professional burnout, therefore stressing the need for psycho-emotional elements of the work environment. This suggests that stress and burnout should be considered interrelated characteristics of professional practice that are relevant to satisfaction with professional realization.

Findings point to a need for interventions aimed at improving organizational climate, reducing additional workload, supporting professional development, and promoting healthy behaviors among Master of Pharmacy professionals. Such measures could contribute not only to higher professional satisfaction but also to lowering stress and reducing the risk of professional burnout.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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